

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MUSICAL HEARING

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Abstract: It is known that there are different forms of hearing, one of them and the most important one is musical hearing. In turn, there are several types of musical hearing. This article discusses the description and forms of musical hearing.

Key words: Music culture, form, musical hearing, melodic, harmonic, rhythm, note, musical pitch.

Introduction.

One of the most important aspects of understanding music is the presence of a developed musical hearing. Musical hearing is the ability to perceive all elements of music: intonation, nuance, rhythm and phrasing. There are people with absolute (absolute) hearing, who can determine the pitch without matching this sound to the sound on the instrument. Most people have relative hearing loss.

Relative hearing includes all types of musical hearing: melodic, harmonic, chord, polyphonic, internal.

One of the most important types is internal hearing, which is the ability to express musical sounds using the musical imagination. Beethoven had such hearing, he created great works despite his deafness.

Musical hearing can and should be developed. The musical cycle program provides a theme for development - solfeggio, but lessons on the instrument play an important role. From the first lessons, the teacher works on the development of musical hearing: he first offers to repeat small songs, pays attention to the movement of the melody and the change of the pitch of the sounds relative to each other, the speed of the music, the quality of the sound, the rhythmic form of the piece, controls its character, gradually complicates the material. The effect of musical form on hearing should be emphasized. Its correct alignment does not leave the ear indifferent for a minute. The main goal is to develop the student's listening skills by performing the following tasks:

- Teach the proper distribution of fingers on the keyboard, feel the keyboard, and read from a sheet using touch;
- Step into the world of sounds through performance practices;
- Get into the habit of listening to sounds and their length and combination;
- Introducing the song with folk motifs by singing vocals;
- Teach to hear the beauty of harmonic turns, giving bright features of the sound of intervals, chords;
- Learning to perceive sound as alive, vibrating, pulsating;
- Teaching musical expressions, basics of musical form;

- Vocal singing, the development of sensitivity and sensitivity to music, performing Will, activity and other personal characteristics are important for performance.

The structure of musical hearing is not easy and very soft, it requires careful treatment. The structure of the nervous system of the auditory system is very complex. In fact, this device itself is a musical device. For a musician, the most interesting part of the labyrinth of the ear is the cochlea. It has something called Membrana basilaris. It is a whole series of elongated fibers of various lengths and configurations that can be called auditory structures. All these strings form a whole musical system of strings, like a Harp. But in addition, there are higher musical centers of the brain:

- musical ideas;
- concepts;
- thought centers (*inner hearing center*).

Affects the hearing condition of the performer - mood and external noise, disturbing sounds, nervous behavior of the teacher (*if it is a lesson*), noise in the hall (if it is a concert). Sometimes it happens that the student has not established a creative mood. The reason for this may be a bad mood or fatigue accumulated during the day. It is necessary to find words that will mobilize his energy. It can be a story about the shape of the piece, images of musical themes, or the nature of music. The performance of the teacher, his character and good attitude towards the student are also important here. It is at that moment that fantasy is ignited, the richness of colors, the beauty of nuances are revealed, and Inspiration is born. It is very important that the performer is in good condition - in this case, his perception of the sound will be clear and sensitive. In the lessons, the teacher tells the students about the need to mentally conduct the performance, review the performance plan. This is an important moment of creative attitude to performance.

For some time, the student is focused and ready to perceive sound waves, this attention should be supported by artistic and performance tasks, because the performer's hobby keeps the hearing in a state of tone. If external noises occur during performance, then the whole mass of auditory structures in the ears in the organ of Corti, in its nerve hairs, will be in the most disordered state, irritation will appear.

This kind of chaos dulls the entire perceptual nervous system for a while, because it is well known that the rapid change of chaotic, inconsistent impressions is very tiring for our senses. This condition of the organ of Corti worsens the general hearing condition. Hearing loses the ability to clearly perceive musical sounds for a while, becomes dull, just as our fatigue does not disappear immediately. If outside noise or conversation is heard during the game, it is for the nervous system of the auditory organ as if someone has washed something someone else has drawn from the board.

A musician's hearing is affected not only by external sound, but also by various unnatural sounds and bad music. Do not do it mechanically, tire the hearing and nervous system and repeat difficult cycles many times.

In works written for vocal performance and orchestra, nuances from PP to FF, sound of drums, articulation of sounds have a great impact on auditory development; the change of shades has a beneficial effect. The main thing is that the shadows are not colorless, weak, disproportionate (*especially crescendo and diminuendo*).

Successful development of musical hearing is possible only when working with sound as an artistic material. There are many ways to develop musical hearing. Each teacher chooses the most suitable methods of work for him and his students.

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